

INTERNET RESOURCES AS A LEARNING TOOL FOR THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The demands placed on higher language education, student growth as a whole, and program efficacy are significant in today's society. The educator can tackle this challenging issue with the use of contemporary information technology, such as the Internet, in addition to traditional teaching strategies. The use of online materials in the classroom has made education more mobile, rigorously differentiated, and interactive. A modern computer can do the tasks of a TV, book, calculator, phone, and other devices. It is regarded as a universal tool that can swiftly and efficiently meet the needs of students. Nevertheless, a computer serves as a tool that, when utilized properly, greatly boosts the pedagogical process' efficacy, not as a replacement for the instructor.

Keywords: *mastering, autonomous learning, intercultural communication, incorporate, self-assurance, psychological traits, interaction abilities, interactivity, authenticity*

The development of communicative skills is the primary objective of teaching foreign languages in higher education. The ability to engage with people from different cultures and to communicate in a foreign language are both included in the category of communicative competence. This objective fully aligns with the fundamental organizational principle of the Internet, which is network communication. All that the Internet really is a vast language space, or better yet, a global community that communicates online. By using the Internet, a unique informational and educational environment that simulates real-world voice interaction can be created. Digital realm Through the internet, you may plan genuine dialog about current themes at a time and location that is convenient for you, transcending time and distance. At the moment, foreign language instruction in higher education The following services can be found on the Internet as a resource for information and education. One can utilize various online resources such as

dictionaries, encyclopedias, directories, websites of TV and radio channels, electronic versions of newspapers and magazines, websites of professional public and commercial organizations, online courses, tests, training programs, libraries, and catalogs. Other options include creating your own webpage, video conferences, electronic mail, and online chat. Internet resources are currently utilized in the educational process as a communication tool, information source, and method of autonomous learning or education enhancement. Students' interaction abilities and genuine communication in a foreign language are formed and developed as a result of using online tools for learning.

In the global network, mastering English is mainly about mastering a relevant semantic system rather than a specific grammatical rule or linguistic structure. The learner focuses his attention on studying the meaning of statements in order to make sense of what he saw and heard. He next examines the structure that is provided. The foundation of traditional techniques to teaching a foreign language is language as a system; internet communication teaches communication in English. Internet technologies aid in the development of a student's social and psychological traits, self-assurance, and teamwork skills in addition to language proficiency. Grades are not displayed on the Internet, which increases motivation to learn. The development of intercultural competency, which happens in the process of learning about the cultural realities of the nations where the language is being studied, is one of the benefits of using internet resources in foreign language instruction at universities. Numerous websites are available on the Internet to help develop effective intercultural communication skills.

In order to achieve this, the university's foreign language classes provide students with the opportunity to visit the following websites, which are jam-packed with real linguistic and non-linguistic content; they can also plan virtual travels to different nations and cities, stop at renowned museums and other sites, explore the city and metro; and they can even book hotel rooms, flights, and trains online. Websites:- <https://www.flash.net/cssmithl/vr/htm> , -www.subwavnavigatir.com; www.citv.net

Multimedia technologies are the combination of computer technologies, simultaneously using several information environments: graphics, text, video, animation, sound effects. In other words, multimedia involves the presentation of information in various forms at the same time (using sound, graphics, video, animation, etc.). It is worth noting that today the Internet acts as a qualitatively new media, combining video, text, audio, graphic etc. [Warschauer,2011].

Today most researchers (West, K. C., Kajder, S., Bull, G.) recognize that multimedia and digital technologies have tremendous didactic and methodical

potential. Within the framework of the competence approach to learning the main purpose of learning a foreign language is the development of communicative competence and its components (in particular, information and communicative / digital competence). The means of achieving this goal is the development of foreign language skills (grammatical, lexical, phonetic) and abilities (reading, listening, speaking) [West, 2008], [Kajder,2004].

Currently, there are many diverse means of new information technologies; and the computer takes a special place among those used in the educational process. Investigation of the problems of computer training in foreign languages occupies one of the main places in the works of scientists such as Blood, R., Thorne, S. L., Payne, J. S. The introduction of a computer to the educational process leads to the emergence of new organizational forms of training. At the stage of presenting a new educational material, students have the opportunity for direct contact with other trainees and with a new learning content submitted through Internet resources [Blood,2012],[Thorne,2005].

In the sphere of application of information and communication technologies in learning foreign languages a great contribution was made by R. E. Ferdig. He notes that “currently the didactic properties and functions of new multimedia and hypermedia technologies in the field of learning foreign languages are actively investigated, various aspects of Internet use are being developed” [Ferdig,2007].

The best way to teach a foreign language at a university and make the process enjoyable and engaging is without a doubt through the use of online resources. However, it should be noted that the Internet can only serve as an extra technical teaching tool when properly included into the educational process; it cannot, by itself, take the place of a teacher in the classroom. Internet resources can be used in foreign language lessons (English) at a non-linguistic university to learn many facets of the English language: - imparting English listening and pronunciation skills.

Listening to contemporary musical compositions can make the process of learning to listen engaging and enjoyable. Nowadays, there are a lot of websites on the Internet that offer music lyrics in both English and Russian. You can utilize a pre-made, professional translation at initially, but in the long run, you should strive to translate every word on your own; otherwise, the training won't have much of an impact. Our memory will naturally recall how to pronounce words that are already familiar to us as time goes on and the lyrics and terminology become plain to us. This approach is beneficial as well since it allows us to better grasp the local culture by comprehending the meaning of the music we are listening to. Not only do you hear what is being spoken, but you also see a picture in front of you. English-language films produce this kind of visual sequence for the spoken words. As a result, viewing

English-language movies is a great way to practice listening comprehension and accurate pronunciation. It also gives you a chance to become familiar with slang words. The following technology is used to educate English language learners how to listen comprehension through films. A movie with Russian subtitles is the first thing you should look for, as dubbed movies are inappropriate for educational purposes. Next, locate the same movie and watch it multiple times with English subtitles.

You must listen to well-known phrases while watching, focusing on the context in which they are said as well as how they organically sound. The film must be divided into semantic fragments in order to achieve the required comprehension and memorization of new lexical units, learn how to pronounce them correctly for the teacher, and develop a set of exercises to relieve basic language difficulties prior to, during, and after viewing.

Students can locate the relevant information published in the following print magazines on the website page:

1. Information can be found on five headings on THE WASHINGTON POST (<http://www.washingtonpost.com/>): news, lifestyle, sports (sports), ads (classifieds), and market news (marketplace);

2. <http://cnn.com/world> CNN World News;

3. ABC News (<http://www.abcnews.go.com/index.html>) provides local audio and video content, a CHAT service, and the capacity to set up discussion boards for readers to engage in on the articles' content;

4. Students with varying levels of English competence can listen to content based on printed text at the required speaking speed through BBC World Service (<http://www.bbc.co.uk/worldservice>);

5. Lesson materials are available for less money at The Washington Times (<http://www.washtimes.com/>);

6. The New York Times (<http://www.nytimes.com/>).

An essential resource for learning to read English is online newspapers. University classes can use the content from these publications to teach viewing, summarizing, and close reading. The concept of individualization and a differentiated approach to learning can be put into practice by using various article sections and topics. For instance, weak students can learn about the content of articles about culture and traditions, while strong students can learn about the advancements in science and technology. A valuable source of current knowledge for research projects, creative assignments, and autonomous work is first-hand experience from online newspapers and magazines. The language of the press is a vast lexical foundation of contemporary English, which can be used to greatly increase vocabulary, create topical catalogs of professional and colloquial vocabulary, create electronic

dictionaries and encyclopedias, electronic books and libraries, and teach writing using online resources.

Teachers must, however, skillfully include the English language learning approach of one-on-one contact. The idea is that personal letters don't necessarily have content that can help someone improve their command of a foreign language since the topics covered in them don't always relate to the issues facing society today. Students frequently struggle with a lack of vocabulary and conversation starters. Therefore, the entire lesson shouldn't be devoted to email communication; instead, the teacher should use this kind of activity sparingly in the classroom. For instance, they could conduct a survey on the lesson's subject, get students' opinions on a particular issue, or just ask a question that interests them.

A non-linguistic university can incorporate language multimedia materials on professional issues into its English language education program, placing students in an authentic professional setting and providing them with the interactive opportunity to make judgments on their own in a variety of professional scenarios. Beyond the formal linguistic experience gained by telecommunications, it is impossible to deny the development of intercultural competency.

The project methodology is in line with a cooperative learning strategy, which is group-based learning. Through project activities, students' knowledge is expanded and deepened by making connections with the lesson's educational material. A non-linguistic university can incorporate language multimedia materials on professional issues into its English language education program, placing students in an authentic professional setting and providing them with the interactive opportunity to make judgments on their own in a variety of professional scenarios. Beyond the formal linguistic experience gained by telecommunications, it is impossible to deny the development of intercultural competency.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that the Internet provides many opportunities to improve the quality of teaching a foreign language. It is an excellent assistant in organizing the educational process, namely, in teaching various types of speech activity forming psychology of environmentally responsible behavior of the students. But despite of the many obvious advantages of the Internet, many specialists who actively use it in their teaching practice and promote the introduction of new technologies in the educational process emphasize the need for a rational, methodologically justified use of the Internet within classroom lessons in a foreign language. The communicative method involves learning to communicate and the formation of the ability for intercultural interaction which is considered the basis for the functioning of the Internet. Nowadays preference is given to communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, the study of

the English language in a cultural context. Now modern methods with the introduction of Internet resources are opposed to classical teaching of the English language. To teach communication in English, it is necessary to explore real, true actual situations that will initiate the study of the material and contribute to adequate behavior. This problem can be corrected by modern technologies, in particular by the Internet. One of the leading requirements for teaching English with the Internet resources is the interactivity. By teaching a foreign language, the Internet can help develop speaking skills and abilities, as well as teaching vocabulary and grammar, providing true effectiveness.

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